

IMAGES OF MOTHERHOOD IN CONTEMPORARY PAINTING OF
UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of paintings depicting different images of motherhood in modern Uzbek painting. Paintings by Javlon Umarbekov, Bakhodir Jalalov, Akmal Nur and Akmal Ikramdjanov.

Keywords: motherhood, modern painting, style, cult theme, image, modern language of painting, idea of composition, colorfulness, philosophy of color.

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Abstract: Данная статья посвящается изучению картин, где изображены разные образы материнства в современной живописи Узбекистана. Картины Джавлона Умарбекова, Баходира Джалалова, Акмаля Нура и Акмаля Икрамджанова.

Keywords: материнство, современная живопись, стиль, культовая тематика, образ, современный язык живописи, замысел композиции, красочность, философия цвета.

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Abstract: Ushbu maqola O'zbekiston zamonaviy rangtasvirida onalikning turli obrazlarini aks ettiruvchi rasmlarni o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Javlon Umarbekov, Bahodir Jalolov, Akmal Nur va Akmal Ikromjonovlarning asarlari.

Keywords: onalik, zamonaviy rangtasvir, uslub, kult mavzulari, tasvir, zamonaviy rangtasvir tili, kompozitsion g'oya, rang-baranglik, rang falsafasi.

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Motherhood is one of the most significant values of a person. And that is why the image of motherhood has always attracted the attention of representatives of many sciences, art and culture. The image of the mother is famous not only for tenderness, kindness, but also for great willpower, resistance to any troubles and sorrows. There are many works of art dedicated to the mother woman in the world. The sublime and reverent attitude to the image of the mother is one of the traditions of art. They express love, gratitude, worship, respect and many other feelings for the mother. The topic of motherhood has always occupied a huge place in many world cultures. The image of motherhood is the ideal of a mother, which is passed down from generation to generation. Mother is a symbol of life, holiness, eternity, warmth and love. The image of motherhood is expressed by the masters as a spiritual path, as a feat, but also as the greatest happiness. Maternal love fills the

world with light and love. A mother gives life to her child, protects and protects him, gives him her infinite love and tenderness. The unity of the child and the mother is an eternal continuous connection. At all times, the close attention of artists was attracted by the image of the Mother. The image of the mother, the unity of mother and child is an eternal theme of art. The great images of motherhood at different times and in different countries were sung by artists using the means of artistic expression peculiar to that time. Therefore, the theme is inexhaustible and will always excite artists, since the feeling of love for the mother cannot be expressed by any painting.

Many artists of Uzbekistan have devoted a large number of works to this topic. New images of motherhood in modern Uzbek painting are especially interesting. Let's look at them using the example of paintings by Javlon Umarbekov, Bakhodir Jalalov, Akmal Nur and Akmal Ikramdjanov.

The artist Javlon Umarbekov is in constant creative search, experimenting, creating more and more new works. To create for him is like breathing. In his life and work, he created his own trajectory of the path, and many young artists are following him today. Javlon Umarbekov works practically not only in different techniques, but also in all genres, the range of his choice of themes, plots, images, genres is quite large and diverse. Landscapes, still lifes, portraits, historical scenes, as well as conditional compositions reveal different facets of the artist's thematic preferences. He is interested in history and modernity, real and illusory, individual and generalized, resulting in a unique work of art. The peculiarity of the artist's skill is that he can elevate an ordinary motif to the level of generalization. In the artist's works, his inner world is clearly read, creative and constructive, harmonious and balanced, national and universal.

Madonna and Child

Javlon Umarbekov's creative handwriting is an individual interpretation of Cubist principles, bright and sonorous color, national motifs, continuity and innovation, experiments with modernism, the avant-garde of the twentieth century. His work "Madonna and Child" is a vivid example of this. The painting

"Madonna and Child" is an amazing combination of cult themes and new Cubist principles, avant-garde and national motif. Javlon Umarbekov is an artist of his land, an artist of the twentieth century, in which the original spiritual values of the East and universal values of world culture were assimilated. His creative principles have been mastered and are being mastered by the next generations of Uzbek artists, thereby once again proving their viability and harmony, philosophy and wisdom.

This is an artist who became a classic of the Uzbek national fine art during his lifetime. Javlon Umarbekov, having absorbed the best traditions of world art, gives them further life and development. This is a rare gift that is not given to every artist. He can have a dialogue with the heritage on an equal footing. His spiritual world, like the spiritual world of his predecessors, carries humanistic values, ideas of goodness, creativity, beauty, which the artist conveys in the language of modern art, with his original creative searches. And this gives the right to add Javlon Umarbekov to the golden fund of world art, in which he will take his rightful place. Javlon Umarbekov is a People's Artist of Uzbekistan, a full member of the Academy of Arts of the Republic, professor of the Kamoliddin Behzad National Institute of Arts and Design. This artist is one of the key figures of contemporary art in Uzbekistan. The artist's creativity is nurtured by the rich cultural and historical tradition and heritage of his people and inspired by the powerful charge of world art. It is no exaggeration to say that in the starry row of the great masters of our time there is a place that is worthily occupied by the People's Artist of Uzbekistan, academician Zhavlon Umarbekov. The paintings of this artist immediately literally fascinate a lot of lovers and fans of painting. They make you think about a lot, rethink a lot. They find a true reflection of both the pages of the history of our region and modernity. The event is the opening of each of his solo exhibitions. They cause lively discussions and discussions. Appreciating the contribution of Javlon Umarbekov to the development of the fine arts of our country at the opening ceremony, Chairman of the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan Akmal Nuriddinov said that this is an artist who became a classic of the national fine arts during his lifetime. Having absorbed the best traditions of world art, he saturates them with new facets and content. We can say with full confidence that Javlon Umarbekov is one of the outstanding artists of Uzbekistan.

His spiritual world carries humanistic values, ideas of goodness, creativity and beauty, which the artist conveys in the language of modern art, with his original creative searches. In this and other speeches, it was emphasized that Umarbekov works in all genres, both his paintings and graphic canvases are deeply impressive. Historical scenes, portraits of great representatives of the past and present, landscapes and still lifes reveal different facets of his creative palette, connecting

the past with modern motifs. as a result, there are unique works of art. And all this can be seen in various halls of the gallery, starting with such brilliant canvases as "Reasonable Man", "I am a man", "In the gardens of Chigatai" and magnificent works of recent years "Mother and Child", "Full Moon", "Tahir and Zuhra", "At the spring", "Family from the Tuareg tribe", "Venice" and others. Umarbekov's paintings are successfully demonstrated at the most prestigious exhibitions in our country and abroad.

He works in various techniques, ranging from simple drawings to easel graphics. All types, directions and genres of graphics:- pencil drawing, watercolor, gouache, print, linocut, etching, etc. "I like to work on black paper, I invented it myself, discovered it. I used a white felt-tip pen, acrylic, somewhere pastel, I like to experiment in every possible way. Very often, on the basis of these experiments, works of complex easel graphics are obtained."- says the artist. Javlon Umarbekov is one of the most prominent representatives of modern fine art. His work is filled with the rich cultural and historical tradition and artistic heritage of the Uzbek people, inspired by the interaction of the cultures of the East and West. In Umarbekov's works, one can see the theme of national history and the activities of its outstanding representatives - people reflecting historical time. In his paintings, the artist depicts the fate, the grandeur of the universe and the place of man in it. His canvases are about life, about the eternal life of the soul, about sorrows and joys, hope and despair, and of course - about love. Each painting by the author is a separate parable told by the artist with a deep philosophical meaning.

This is an artist who, from his first creative beginnings, became one of the unique creative personalities in the history of the artistic culture of Uzbekistan of the twentieth century. An artist who has had a huge impact not only on the fine arts of Uzbekistan, but also on the art of the Central Asian region. An artist whose work is included in the golden fund of world art.

Bakhodir Jalalov is a muralist, People's Artist of Uzbekistan. The artist became widely known thanks to the monumental works performed in the 80s of the XX century in different cities of Uzbekistan: The painting "Harvest" in the club of the pumping station in Talimarjan (1983); The fresco "The Birth of dance" in the former concert hall "Bahor" (1982).

The works of Bakhodir Jalalov amaze with a combination of three unities: the power of design, the logic of composition, the grace of fine plastic. It can be a philosophy of color, color and light, or maybe color, light and thought.

The birth of dance (fragment) Harvest (fragment)

On the fragment of the painting "The Birth of Dance" we see the image of the Uzbek Madonna and child. Very lyrical, the lines are elegant. The artist celebrates the image of motherhood, the characters are a young mother with a child, the type of characters is not European, but Asian. The work is magical and mysterious. Takes the viewer into another reality, into eternity.

On the fragment of the painting "Harvest" we see a different image of motherhood. The mother is a worker of the field, the image of local women of the village. The work is done in an avant-garde style. A familiar theme and a combination of the modern language of painting. The work is colorful, fresh and new.

Bakhodir Fazletdinovich, like his work, is versatile and multifaceted. His works include admiration for the masters of the Italian Renaissance, a tribute to Russian artistic traditions, the embodiment of unique Central Asian motifs, and very successful samples in avant-garde. The filigree of the execution of the graphics of Bakhodir Jalalov, who passed the classical "study" of the Russian and Italian drawing schools, is rare. The picturesque canvases are full of symbols, where the earth and the sky unite to give birth to the truth, which, like a philosopher's stone, the artist tries to get through creative experience.

Before the first works of Bakhodir Jalal were created, freed from the objectivity of the real world, the artist made bright independent breakthroughs to the experience of European modernism, to the heritage of the East, which were supported by his intuitive metaphysical insights and very personal immersion in philosophical and spiritual experience. It is this mobility of soul and thought, openness and impulsiveness of searches that is a bright feature of the master's individuality. The artist, being able to brilliantly give out classical representation, without departing from it, and in parallel with it, easily plunges into the "unconscious" flow of forms, close to abstract surrealism.

Leonardo's Mother

In the painting "Leonardo's Mother", the artist created an image of motherhood, in which he is inspired by the masters of the Italian Renaissance, the figure is painted in a classical artistic manner, and the background is mysterious, conditional. The intertwined braids of the character are raised to the top, and each pigtail is held by little angels. The hair, in general, created the image of a crown worn on the character. The figure is half submerged in water and there is one fish on the water. Pisces are symbols of peace, harmony, tranquility and life. The color of the painting is warm, golden. The painting celebrates motherhood in all its glory. Such an image of motherhood has not yet been created by Uzbek masters and is becoming, in its own way, a unique creation.

Akmal Nur is an Oriental artist in his attitude, not because he is Uzbek, but because he follows in his work the deep spiritual traditions of the artistic culture of the East. This is the path that Kamoliddin Bekhzod, Muhammad Murad Samarqandi, and in the twentieth century Alexander Volkov, Usto Mumin, Chingiz Akhmarov chose. Art for him is not just a profession, it is a spiritual practice, during which he strives for the perfection of his soul.

Motherhood

The Divine Ray

The birth of a child is a bright event, preceded by the history of the parents' relationship, and the child himself is given by God. Akmal Nur always tries to look

deeper into the soul of the created image. He does not care about the exact external details, facial features, similarities.

Akmal himself believes that he is still the bearer of an eastern philosophical view of the world and life. He poetizes the East, but at the same time, does not idealize it, leaving everything as it is. Akmal Nur is an experimenter who gives the subtle East new colors, adding expressive tones and sounds. Akmal Nur's paintings are designed in a calm, discreet color scheme, and sometimes seem to be sketches, easily and naturally transferred to the canvas. The female images embodied in the master's works are peculiar. As a rule, these are refined oriental maidens, with long curly hair, slightly elongated necks, emphasizing their grace, with thoughtfulness, sometimes with an imprint of sadness on their face. Akmal Nur is one of the brightest representatives of artists of the Uzbek school of fine arts, who widely uses symbolism in his works. So in his works there are pomegranate, apple or stones symbolizing fertility, love and sadness, fish – a symbol of purity.

People's Artist of Uzbekistan, academician of the Academy of Arts Akmal Ikramdjanov works in a traditional way. Like many artists of our time, he tried his hand at various genres of painting. He was influenced by the great classics of world painting, as well as our modern artists. His works demonstrate a deep assimilation of the traditions of the world school of realistic art, their combination with national themes and color. From the very first steps, his interest in the portrait genre was also determined. His canvases, created over forty years of creativity, were included in the golden fund of the national painting of Uzbekistan. The artist tends to realism, combining it with the plasticity of images and the depth of psychological study of characters.

In the painting "Generosity" (the left part of the diptych), the artist depicted a mother with children. The painting is very colorful, fresh, bright in color, the familiar theme is written in a modern manner. A new, bright, collage, modernistic

Generosity

Family (diptych)

approach helped to reveal the images and plot, which makes the picture attractive.

Valley of Mothers

The painting "Valley of Mothers" (1998) depicts mothers, Oriental women in the image of a young daughter-in-law and her mother-in-law. The painting is painted in a warm color. The warmth in the painting reveals the essence of the work - maternal warmth, our sunny land and the character of the Eastern people. The artist also demonstrated his virtuoso writing, the materiality of each element of the painting is felt in the letter. The painting is painted in the direction of hyperrealism. With this wonderful painting inspired by maternal warmth, the artist presented the world with images of motherhood in the guise of our Uzbek women.

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